

STUDENTS' CONCEPTUAL UNDERSTANDING THROUGH EXPERIENTIAL LEARNING WITH 3-D VECTOR APPARATUS

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ABSTRACT

Experiential learning through the 3-D vector apparatus allows students to explore and manipulate vectors actively, enhancing their problem-solving skills, attitudes, and conceptual mastery through hands-on engagement and reflective thinking. This study investigates students' conceptual understanding of vectors through experiential learning with 3-D vector apparatus. The study utilized a one-group pretest-posttest design involving 108 first-year engineering students at Central Mindanao University during the second semester of the school year 2023-2024. The Certainty of Response Index (CRI) was used in the vector test questionnaire to categorize students' conceptual understanding as Knowledge of Correct Concepts, Misconceptions, or Lack of Knowledge. Results show significantly improved students' knowledge of correct concepts across all vector topics (vector components, unit vector, and vector operations), with reduced misconceptions in vector components. However, there were persisting misconceptions related to resultant vector magnitudes, directions, and methods of vector addition (e.g., parallelogram and polygon methods). While experiential learning with the 3-D vector apparatus improves knowledge of correct concepts, further interventions are needed to address persistent misconceptions.

Keywords: *conceptual understanding, vectors, experiential learning, misconceptions*

INTRODUCTION

Vectors are one of the topics in physics that students find challenging to grasp as they struggle to visualize its concepts, which may impede their understanding and lead to negative attitudes toward physics. Vectors are fundamental concepts in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM), as they are the foundational knowledge for advanced concepts in STEM-related courses. Developing countries such as the Philippines must produce knowledgeable and competent graduates in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics, as they play a crucial role in national development (ISTIC, 2015).

In Region X, an increasing dropout rate among STEM students was recorded from Academic Year 2017 to 2021. A lack of foundational knowledge in STEM subjects, especially physics, often discourages students and is further compounded by the declining number of peers entering the strand (Alvarez, 2024). Furthermore, according to the PISA 2022 results, Filipino high school students lagged among Southeast Asian countries in scientific and mathematical proficiency. These findings reflect the challenges and difficulties science students face, including physics.

Sabah (2023) and Bani-Salameh et al. (2020) identified challenges in students' understanding of vectors, including difficulties with the graphical representation of unit vectors, vector addition and subtraction, and interpreting dot and cross products. In addition, Jewaru et al. (2021) found that students have persisting difficulties in the physical representation of vectors despite correct responses in the mathematical tests.

Integrating hands-on experiences influences students' grasp of physics concepts that may shape their conceptual understanding in physics by engaging learners in hands-on activities and real-world applications. For instance, Santhalia and Yuliati (2021) demonstrated that experiential, phenomenon-based instruction significantly enhanced students' scientific literacy and understanding of projectile motion. Estianinur et al. (2021) further showed that combining experiential learning with formative assessments and practical tasks improved students' grasp of static fluid concepts.

While experiential learning has positively affected conceptual understanding of projectile motion and fluid mechanics, studies about its influence on students' conceptual understanding of vectors remain limited. Jewaru et al. (2021) emphasize the need for educational tools to enhance students' exploration of vectors. Addressing this gap, Dr. Cecilia O. Bucayong's 3-D Instructional Vector Apparatus for Vector Operations provides an interactive, experiential learning environment that helps students explore and calculate vector operations more effectively.

This study examined students' conceptual understanding of vectors through experiential learning with the 3-D vector apparatus. The findings of this study may provide relevant insights for curriculum developers, school administrators, and teachers to use the 3-D vector apparatus to facilitate students' conceptual understanding of vectors in an experiential learning environment.

Research Questions

This study examined students' conceptual understanding of vectors through experiential learning with 3-D vector apparatus. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of students' conceptual understanding of vector concepts in the pre-test and post-test when exposed to experiential learning with 3-D vector apparatus in terms of:
 - a. Knowledge of Correct Concepts;
 - b. Misconceptions; and
 - c. Lack of Knowledge?
2. Is there a significant difference between the students' conceptual understanding in the pre-test and post-test when exposed to experiential learning with the 3-D vector apparatus?

METHODOLOGY

The study utilized a one-group pretest-posttest design to examine students' conceptual understanding of vectors through experiential learning using the 3-D vector apparatus. This design was selected due to the absence of a control group, as all participants were exposed to the same intervention involving the manipulation of the 3-D vector apparatus.

The study involved 108 first-year engineering students from Central Mindanao University during the 2nd semester of the 2023-2024 academic year. These participants are enrolled in the Engineering Science subject offered by the Physics Department at the College of Arts and Sciences. Engineering Science subject incorporates vector topics into its course syllabus. Study participants are enrolled in the laboratory class of the subject and have prior knowledge about vectors gained during their lecture class.

A researcher-made vector conceptual test assessed students' conceptual understanding of vectors. It consisted of multiple-choice items based on the topics: unit vectors in 3-D, component vectors, vector addition, dot product, and cross product. In the beginning, the researcher-made test was checked for validity by three physics faculty to ensure its reliability. Following validation, the questionnaire was pilot-tested at Bukidnon National School of Home Industries (BNSHI) to Senior High School STEM students (S.Y. 2023-2024) who have already taken up vector topics and manipulated the 3-D vector apparatus. The reliability coefficient was equivalent to 0.75, indicating that the test items were reliable, of which 30 items were retained considering Bloom's Taxonomy.

The Certainty of Response Index (CRI) was incorporated into the researcher-made vector conceptual test to assess students' certainty in answering vector concepts. It consisted of a six-point scale (from 0 to 5) in which 0 implies no knowledge (total guess) of methods or laws required for answering a particular question. At the same time, 5

indicated high confidence in understanding the principles to arrive at the selected answer. The modified CRI scale by Madina et al. (2022) is below.

Table 1. Certainty of Response Index (CRI) by Madina et al. (2022)

CRI		Criteria	Confidence Level
0	Totally guess answer	The percentage of guess elements is 100%.	
1	Almost a guess	The percentage of guess elements is between 75%-99%.	Low
2	Not sure	The percentage of guess elements is between 50%-74%.	
3	Sure	The percentage of guess elements is between 25%-49%.	
4	Almost certain	The percentage of guess elements is between 1%-24%.	High
5	Certain	The percentage of guess elements is between 0%	

When the level of certainty is low (CRI ranging from 0 to 2), it suggests that determining the answer involves significant guesswork and low confidence. Despite the correct answer, a CRI of zero usually means a student is just guessing with no fundamental understanding. On the other hand, with a high CRI (ranging from 3 to 5), the respondent expressed a high confidence in the chosen laws and methods employed to reach the answer. A correct answer would validate the high certainty level in such cases (CRI of 3–5). However, if the answer is incorrect, the high certainty indicates a misplaced confidence in understanding the subject matter. This misplaced certainty in applying specific laws and methods to a particular question suggests the presence of misconceptions. Below is the modified decision matrix of Hasan et al. (1999) based on the combinations of correct or wrong answers and of low or high CRI.

Table 2. Conceptual Understanding Category based on Students' Responses and Certainty of Response Index

Answer	CRI	Confidence Level	Category
Right	≥ 3	High	Knowledge of Correct Concepts
Right	≤ 2	Low	Lack of Knowledge (lucky guess)
Wrong	≥ 3	High	Misconceptions
Wrong	≤ 2	Low	Lack of Knowledge

Based on students' responses, the following three categories could be drawn: Knowledge of Correct Concepts (KC), Misconceptions (MC), and Lack of Knowledge

(LK). The percentage in each category was obtained using the equation below (Madina et al., 2022).

$$P = \frac{f}{N} \times 100\%$$

P is the percentage number of students' responses in every category. f is the frequency of students' responses (per category), and N is the number of students.

The percentage in each category was interpreted based on the study of Istighfarin, L. (2015) percentage distribution to determine the level of students' knowledge of correct concepts (KC), misconceptions (MC), and lack of knowledge (LK).

Table 3. Conceptual Understanding Percentage Level Interpretation

Percentage	Interpretation
0% - 30%	Low
31% - 60%	Moderate
61% - 100%	High

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 4 presents the percentage of students' conceptual understanding of vectors regarding knowledge of correct concepts in the pretest and posttest results.

Table 4. Percentage of Students' Conceptual Understanding of Vectors in terms of Knowledge of Correct Concepts

Vector Concept	Knowledge of Correct Concepts			
	Pretest		Posttest	
	Percentage (%)	Qualitative Interpretation	Percentage (%)	Qualitative Interpretation
Vector components	43.5	Moderate	71.4	High
Unit Vectors	48.1	Moderate	70.2	High
Vector Addition	36.5	Moderate	61.0	High
Vector Multiplication	15.3	Low	56.3	Moderate
OVERALL	35.9	MODERATE	64.7	HIGH

Legend:

Percentage Range

61% - 100%
31% - 60%
0% - 30%

Qualitative Interpretation

High
Moderate
Low

In the pretest, students showed moderate knowledge of correct concepts in vector components, unit vectors, and addition and low knowledge of correct concepts in vector multiplication. After experiential learning with 3-D vector apparatus, students showed increased knowledge of correct concepts in vector components, unit vectors, and vector addition and from low to moderate levels in vector multiplication. The overall percentage of students' knowledge of correct concepts increased from 35.9% in the pretest to 64.7% in the posttest. This means that they are now more confident in their understanding of correct vector concepts through experiential learning with 3-D vector apparatus.

The data reveals that experiential learning with the 3-D vector apparatus effectively increases students' knowledge of correct concepts. They are now more confident in their understanding of vector concepts, which is facilitated by hands-on activity with the 3-D vector apparatus. The findings are supported by the studies of Santhalia and Yuliati (2021) on projectile motion and Estianinur (2021) on fluid mechanics, both of which showed that experiential learning effectively improves students' conceptual understanding of physics concepts.

The results imply that experiential learning with 3-D vector apparatus allows students to visualize their understanding in a physical representation, which gives them more confidence in their understanding and will enable them to evaluate whether it is right or wrong. Hence, experiential learning with 3-D apparatus is a practical instructional approach in facilitating students' exploration of correct vector concepts, specifically performing vector operations.

Table 5 presents the percentage of students' conceptual understanding of vector concepts in terms of misconceptions in the pretest and posttest results.

Table 5. Percentage of Students' Conceptual Understanding of Vectors in terms of Misconceptions

Vector Concept	Misconceptions			
	Pretest		Posttest	
	Percentage (%)	Qualitative Interpretation	Percentage (%)	Qualitative Interpretation
Vector components	12.3	Low	9.4	Low
Unit Vectors	10.1	Low	11.5	Low
Vector Addition	9.4	Low	14.7	Low
Vector Multiplication	14.4	Low	19.3	Low
OVERALL	11.6	LOW	13.7	LOW

Legend:

Percentage Range

- 61% - 100%
- 31% - 60%
- 0% - 30%

Qualitative Interpretation

- High
- Moderate
- Low

In the pretest, students showed a low level of misconceptions about all vector concepts. After experiential learning with 3-D vector apparatus, students' misconceptions about vector components decreased, and unit vectors, vector addition, and vector multiplication slightly increased, yet remained at a low level. The overall percentage of misconceptions among students slightly increased from 11.6% to 13.7%, which means that they have gained increased confidence in their responses, including those that were incorrect, particularly in identifying the direction of the resultant vector relative to the original vectors.

The data reveals that although students developed more confidence in the knowledge of correct concepts (based on the results from Table 4), experiential learning with 3-D vectors may also increase students' confidence in incorrect vector concepts, especially in identifying the direction of the resultant vector and the original vectors. As students are immersed in a hands-on activity with the apparatus, they may commit unnoticed errors in determining the negative and positive axes concerning the x, y, and z axes, contributing to errors in determining the direction of vectors in three dimensions. According to Van Loon et al. (2021), when students feel more confident, they usually become less aware of errors in situations where common mistakes are already present. He discovered that students who had trouble assessing their comprehension were often overconfident answering questions incorrectly.

The results imply that experiential learning with the 3-D vector apparatus requires students to have a solid grasp of vector concepts, especially in Kolb's experiential learning cycle's reflective observation and abstract conceptualization stage. It is crucial to have the correct comprehension of specific concepts during this stage to avoid misconceptions because concepts will be established during this stage and later on will be used in the active experimentation stage. Hence, experiential learning with 3-D vector apparatus requires students to practice repetitively with guided reflection and formative assessment to develop conceptual mastery.

Table 6 presents the percentage of students' conceptual understanding of vector concepts in terms of lack of knowledge in the pretest and posttest results.

Table 6. Percentage of Students' Conceptual Understanding of Vectors in terms of Lack of Knowledge

Vector Concept	Lack of Knowledge			
	Pretest		Posttest	
	Percentage (%)	Qualitative Interpretation	Percentage (%)	Qualitative Interpretation
Vector components	44.2	Moderate	19.2	Low
Unit Vectors	41.8	Moderate	18.3	Low
Vector Addition	54.2	Moderate	24.3	Low
Vector Multiplication	70.4	High	24.4	Low

OVERALL	52.7	MODERATE	21.6	LOW
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Legend:

<u>Percentage Range</u>	<u>Qualitative Interpretation</u>
61% - 100%	High
31% - 60%	Moderate
0% - 30%	Low

In the pretest, students showed a moderate lack of knowledge in vector components, unit vectors, and vector addition and a high lack of knowledge in vector multiplication. After experiential learning with 3-D vector apparatus, students' lack of knowledge of all vector concepts decreased. The overall percentage of lack of knowledge in vectors decreases from 52.7% to 21.6%.

The data reveals that experiential learning with 3-D vector apparatus is effective in decreasing students' lack of knowledge, as their knowledge of correct concepts increased as shown in Table 4. The findings are also supported by the previous studies of Estianinur (2021) and Santhalia and Yuliati (2021) on the positive effects of experiential learning on students' comprehension of physics concepts.

The results imply that experiential learning with 3-D vector apparatus may be effective in facilitating students' exploration of vector components, unit vectors, and vector operations as their knowledge gap decreases. Hence, using 3-D vector apparatus in experiential learning can significantly enhance students' understanding of vector concepts and operations.

Table 7 presents the overall percentage of students' conceptual understanding of vectors in terms of Knowledge of Correct Concepts, Misconceptions, and Lack of Knowledge.

Table 7. Overall Percentage of Students' Conceptual Understanding of Vectors in the Pretest and Posttest

Category	Pretest		Posttest	
	Percentage (%)	Qualitative Interpretation	Percentage (%)	Qualitative Interpretation
Knowledge of Correct Concepts	35.9	Moderate	64.7	High
Misconceptions	11.6	Low	13.7	Low
Lack of Knowledge	52.7	Moderate	21.6	Low

Legend:

<u>Percentage Range</u>	<u>Qualitative Interpretation</u>
61% - 100%	High
31% - 60%	Moderate
0% - 30%	Low

In the pretest, students' knowledge of correct concepts was moderate, misconceptions were low, and lack of knowledge was moderate. As shown in the table, 52.7% of the students lacked knowledge of vector concepts, which means that most students had low confidence in their responses and did not clearly understand vectors despite prior knowledge during the lecture class. While 35.9% of students already knew the correct vector concepts, and 11.6% remained to have misconceptions. After the experiential learning with 3-D vector apparatus, 64.7% of the students now understand correct vector concepts, while 21.6% lacked knowledge, and 13.7% still had misconceptions.

The data reveals a significant transition in students' conceptual understanding from lack of knowledge in the pretest to knowing correct vector concepts in the posttest. The findings suggest that the intervention positively affected students' conceptual understanding of vectors as they became more confident in their correct understanding through direct hands-on exploration where they could visualize and physically engage with vector principles. Experiential learning helps students refine their understanding through the manipulation of the apparatus. The findings of Santhali and Yuliati (2021) and McLeod and Hopfe (2021) supported that experiential learning helps students connect physics concepts to the real world. Hence, using the 3-D vector apparatus supported students in grasping key vector concepts such as direction, magnitude, and vector components and boosted their confidence in their learning.

Table 8 presents the significant difference between students' conceptual understanding of vector concepts. Students' conceptual understanding of most vector concepts shows a significant difference between pretest and posttest results.

Table 8. Difference between students' conceptual understanding of vector concepts in the pretest and posttest

Vector Concept	Pretest %			Posttest %			Chi-square			
	LK	MC	KC	LK	MC	KC	X^2	df	N	p
Vector Components	44.2	12.3	43.5	19.2	9.4	71.4	20.1	2	216	0.000**
Unit Vectors	41.8	10.1	48.2	18.3	11.5	70.2	17.9	2	216	0.494
Vector Addition	54.2	9.4	36.5	24.3	14.7	61.0	30.3	2	216	0.017*
Vector Multiplication	70.4	13.1	16.6	24.4	19.3	56.3	54.6	2	216	0.000**

** *Highly significant at 0.05 level*

* *Significant at 0.05 level*

In the pretest, most of the students lack knowledge in vector components (44.2%), vector addition (54.2%), and vector multiplication (70.4%), while for unit vectors, 48.2% of the students already know correct concepts, indicating that they already have some basic understanding of unit vectors. After experiential learning with 3-D vector apparatus, most of the students now know correct concepts in vector components (71.4%), unit vectors (70.2%), vector addition (61.0%), and vector multiplication (56.3%). There is a

significant transition from lack of knowledge to having knowledge of correct concepts by the students, as evident in p-values, except for unit vectors, which show no significant difference.

The findings suggest that experiential learning with 3-D vector apparatus significantly improved students' knowledge of correct concepts in vectors. The transition from Lack of Knowledge (LK) to Knowledge of Correct Concepts (KC) suggests that hands-on learning helped students visualize and grasp how vectors operate in 3-D. However, the lack of significant difference in students' conceptual understanding of unit vectors indicates that there are still aspects of the concept that students need to understand more deeply, or it may suggest that students had already grasped the idea before the intervention.

Overall, the results imply that experiential learning with the 3-D vector apparatus effectively enhanced students' conceptual understanding of vectors by offering interactive, hands-on experiences to students wherein they could visualize the vector directions in 3-D space. However, the lack of a significant difference in students' understanding of unit vectors, likely due to their prior knowledge of expressing vectors in terms of components using unit vectors, suggests that this concept was already well understood before the intervention. Hence, while the 3-D vector apparatus significantly improved understanding of vector components and operations, its impact on students' basic knowledge of unit vectors was not statistically significant.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

Experiential learning with 3-D vector apparatus improved students' conceptual understanding of vector components, unit vectors, addition, and multiplication. Regarding knowledge of correct concepts, students increased from a moderate level in the pretest to a high level in the posttest. Misconceptions slightly increased but remained low in both pretest and posttest. Meanwhile, the percentage of students categorized under lack of knowledge decreased from a high level in the pretest to a low level in the posttest.

There is a significant difference between students' conceptual understanding of vector concepts in the pretest and posttest following experiential learning with 3-D vector apparatus. An overall increase in knowledge of correct concepts was observed, alongside persistent misconceptions, particularly regarding the magnitude and direction of the resultant vector when applying vector addition methods.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are given:

School administrators and curriculum planners may integrate the 3-D vector apparatus into vector instruction from junior to senior high school, which supports early

conceptual learning, strengthens foundational understanding, and addresses misconceptions.

Teachers are encouraged to conduct regular assessments or reflective activities during the students' hands-on activity with the 3-D vector apparatus to facilitate students' transformation and grasping of knowledge in an experiential learning environment, ensure alignment with correct conceptual understanding, and provide timely feedback on misconceptions.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher obtained a consent letter approved by the Central Mindanao University President with the recommending approval of the Vice-President for Academic Affairs, Director of the Office of Student Affairs, and Dean of the College of Arts and Sciences, noted by the Physics Department Head, Science Education Department Head, and Research Adviser to allow the research to be conducted with full consent and support from the physics department, cooperating instructor, and students observing Data Privacy security measures.

The study followed ethical research standards with great care. Before taking part, students were informed about the purpose of the research in clear, understandable terms, and they agreed to join voluntarily. They signed consent forms that highlighted their right to privacy and assured them that their names and personal information would remain anonymous. All collected data will be handled with strict confidentiality, and no individual will be identified in any part of the study's results.

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